

APPRAISAL OF THE IPOS DURING THE GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS PERIOD

Dr. Dharen Kumar Pandey

*Inspector of Central Excise, CBEC, Govt. of India. Email:
dharenp@gmail.com*

Initial Public Offerings are one of the largest sources of finance to the corporate sector in India. The global financial crisis had, however, affected this source to a larger extent. IPOs have always been a good avenue of investment for the investors. The main objective of the paper is to examine the fluctuations in the prices of IPOs since January, 2007. The paper also tries to focus on the factors behind this volatility. The free pricing of issues, the global recession, and the two-digit inflation have collectively pulled down the IPOs trading volume in the corporate securities market. The most disappointing situation can be seen by comparing the amount raised through IPOs during the period Apr 08–Mar 09 amounting to just Rs. 2096 crores as compared to Rs. 42565 crores in the period Apr 07–Mar 08, a tremendous 95 percent decline. Although the market had recovered to a large extent, the corporate sector still lacked the confidence to opt for IPOs. On the other side, the investors had less to invest into the market due to the high rate of inflation and fear of fluctuating markets.

I. Introduction: Initial Public Offerings (IPOs) are the fresh issues of the shares of a company, to the public with an objective to raise funds. The genesis of IPOs originated from the Dutch East India Company (Verenigde Oostindische Compagnie or VOC in Dutch, literally 'United East Indies Company'), established on March 20, 1602. It was "the first company to issue stocks" (Murali D., 2006). In early 1990s there used to be the Controller of Capital Issues with rigid rules for the new issues. In May, 1992, after the abolition of the Capital Issues (Control) Act, 1947, the issue of capital and pricing of issues by companies had been freed from the requisite of prior approval from the Controller of Capital Issues for certain companies. The IPOs are considered as a good investment avenues by the investors. Domestic companies in India, which raised a total of \$4.6 billion in the first half of the year 2007, have catapulted India to the sixth position in the global list of countries in terms of IPO fund collections (Zachariah R., 2007). However, a good IPO is measured on the basis of following factors such as previous records, if an existing company, underwriters, banker's position, promoter's image and functioning, current market conditions, and world's economy.

The main objective of this paper is to examine the fluctuations in the price of the IPOs, to find out the main factors behind the volatility,

and to provide a better interpretation. The paper also focuses a part towards the performance of the IPOs in recent period. The paper also moves to find out whether the IPOs have supported in capital funding for the Indian companies. The study is based on secondary data. IPOs since January, 2007 have been considered for the analysis. Their issue price, listing price and the current market price have been compared. The price fluctuations at various periods are also compared. Table 1 has been composed for the comparison. The study has been divided into two periods IPOs from Jan 2007 to Dec 2007 and IPOs from Jan 2008 to Sept 2008. Since there has been very low figures of IPOs being issued thereafter, so IPOs and price fluctuations after Sept 2008 are not considered for the study.

II. Relevance of the Study: About half-a-decade has passed. Indian securities market will never forget the drastic fall down of the indices that took place during 2007-09. Many studies have been done in this regard to study the impact of the Global financial crisis. The studies conducted after the arrival of the global financial crisis till date in context of Indian Stock Market has been reviewed as below:

Kumar, R., and Vashisht, P. (2009) claimed that the massive outflow of the FIIs created panic in the stock markets.

Prasad, A. & Reddy, C. P. (2009) studied the impact of the global financial crisis on India and concluded that the financial turmoil affected the stock markets even in India. The combination of a rapid sell off by financial institutions and the prospect of economic slowdown have pulled down the stocks and commodities market.

Thomas, J. J. (2009) emphasizes that the origins of the global financial crisis of the year 2008 date back to the late 1990s. He claimed that the withdrawal of FIIs from India had led to the major collapse of the Indian stock market.

Viswanathan, K. G. (2010) concluded that the global financial crisis which started in 2008 has been adversely affecting all the world economies and the magnitude of its impact is exceeded only by that of the Great Depression of 1930s. He also added that the stock market, which is an indicator of the strength of the economy, has risen by 80% in the first three quarters of the current fiscal year (2009-10), after falling by 38% in the previous year. He stressed that India has been recovering well out of the crunches of the global financial crisis.

Ali, R. & Muhammad, A. (2012) applied EGARCH model to study the impact of global crisis on volatility. The study empirically revealed that negative shocks have more pronounced impact on the volatility than positive shocks. The authors claimed that the recent global financial crisis made mild negative impact on stock returns and enhanced volatility in

Pakistani and Indian stock exchanges but this impact is stronger on Indian stock market.

Bajwa R. (2012) found that the adverse impact on India was mainly in the equity markets because of reversal of portfolio equity flows and the effects on domestic forex markets and liquidity conditions. The contagion of crisis has spread to India even contrary to the ‘decoupling theory’ which says that advanced economies if hit by the crisis would not affect the emerging economies having substantial foreign reserves, improved policy framework, robust corporate balance sheets and healthy banking sector. However, all channels of India were affected by the global crisis.

Mishra, P. K. (2012) attempted to examine the performance of the Indian capital market in terms of market size, market liquidity, market turnover, market volatility, and market efficiency over the period 2008 to 2011. The author concluded that although the capital market of India showed relatively greater degree of volatility and weak form inefficiency during crises, the study found the evidence of the potential for increase in market size, more liquidity and reasonable market turnover.

Walia, S. (2012) found that the foreign investment in India has been growing at a faster rate since 2003-04. However, during 2008-09, the very year hit by the crisis, the foreign investment declined significantly showing a negative growth rate of 31.82 per cent. A similar trend of decline in growth is found in case of income flow to India during 2008-09 and 2009-10. The Indian financial sector was not untouched from the impact of global economic crisis. As the stock markets collapsed in USA and Europe, there was panic in the Indian stock markets. The author concluded that the foreign institutional investors (FIIs) who had invested in Mumbai stock market suddenly withdrew their investment and this naturally dipped the BSE sensex.

Amutha, D. (2013) found that India has been facing major challenges owing to the global financial crisis. The immediate effects were plummeting stock prices, a net outflow of foreign capital, a large reduction in foreign reserves and a sharp tightening of domestic liquidity. These had caused a rapid depreciation of the exchange rate and a surge in short-term interest rates. The second round effects emerged from a slowdown in domestic demand and exports. Demand effects have been particularly severe in housing, construction, consumer durables and the IT sector. As a result, manufacturing production has taken a hit and activities in the organized services sector (housing, construction, IT) are down sharply. Exports declined for two consecutive months in October and November 2008. She also found that the net outflow of FIIs had caused greater harm to the stock markets.

Sakthivel, P. et al. (2014) employed GJR GRACH model to capture asymmetric volatility of NSE and BSE and found that negative news

causes greater volatility impact than positive news. They concluded that the global financial crisis negatively impacted the mean returns and increased the volatility in the Indian stock markets.

None of the studies reviewed above has discussed about the performance of the Initial Public Offerings during the global slowdown. Although few attempts were made to study the impact of the Global financial crisis, its impact upon the IPOs has not been considered. This study proposes to examine the impact of the global slowdown over the Initial Public Offerings. This gap in the literature of Global slowdown will be filled by this study. Hence, this study is surely to add to the literature of finance something new and most needed. Now, as of so late, it is eminent to discuss about the impacts of the financial volcano, now cooled off, that erupted in the United States and the United Kingdom, but the lava of which flowed all over the Globe. Although, India has recovered itself, the scars still exist on the Indian financial market. The indices of the Indian Stock market now have crossed the level from where it fell down. The confidence of the investors has been now built up.

III. Quantitative Analysis: Table 1 reveals that the year 2007 was a very successful year for the IPOs by the corporate sector in India. It can easily be abstracted from the market data that they got a quite well start since their listing. The craze for IPO subscription by the investors was at peak as maximum shares were oversubscribed several times by the investors. The investors knew that the forthcoming market would serve a good rate of return on their funds. IPOs of Omaxe, ICRA, Central Bank of India, Indian Bank, etc all had a very good start and plunged up the market collectively. The IPOs showed their real market feature from the day they got listed on the stock exchange. The IPOs during the end of the year such as Jyothy Lab., BGR Energy Systems Ltd, Power Grid Corp., Consolidated Consortium Co., were subscribed about more than 50 times at BSE and NSE collectively and were listed at about its 1.5 times the issue price. Power Grid Corp. IPO issued in Sept 07 was oversubscribed by 65 times and was listed at Rs.85 making its high close on that same day at Rs.105 issue price being Rs.52 and that BGR Energy Systems Ltd issued in Dec 07 was oversubscribed by 145 times. Though its issue price was Rs.480, yet it was listed at Rs.801.

The market was performing well in the start of the New Year 2008 and it was good for some of the IPOs but their performance was not satisfactory afterwards. Even though the IPO of some companies like Reliance Power, Future Capital Holding, Rural Electric, Aishwarya Telecom, etc were listed at more than their issue prices; their indices later on did not show an impressive performance. The shares of these companies are still suffering due to market slackness. Though the IPO of some companies like Anu's Laboratories, Titagarh Wagons Ltd, Gokul

Refoils, etc are performing well since their issue this year, yet we can also see that some IPOs like 20 Macrons Ltd, Shriram EPC Ltd, KSK Energy Ventures, IRB infrastructure, etc which were listed at less than their issue price and are still the worse performers. Take an example of the Reliance Power IPO with issue price of Rs.450 was listed at Rs.548 and closed at Rs.372 on its first day of trade in the market. On Feb 07, 2008, Wockhardt Hospital pulled out its Rs.676 crore IPO due to under subscription and other business houses were reluctant to move into the primary market. The price band of the book-built issue was lowered from Rs.280-310 to Rs.225-260 and the last date for subscription was extended (Shankaregouda, 2008).

The percentage change in the IPO's issue price and the current market price was negative in thirty-six out of the forty-three IPO's in this study. The issue price of only seven IPO's was found to be more than the current market price. It is evident that the global financial crisis had beaten hard to the growth of the IPO's and the investor's confidence was largely broken down.

The issue of bonus shares by certain companies such as Reliance Power and Birla Cotsyn (India) even was not sufficient to hold back the shares at their expected price. Not only current year issues but also the previous year's good performing IPOs such as Jyothy Lab., BGR Energy Systems Ltd, Consolidated Consortium Co., etc are currently going weak. But when we talk about the public preference, it can still be revealed from the market data that in spite of the poor performance of the market the confidence of the investing public is incorporated in the IPO issues (The case of Wockhardt Hospital being an exception). The rate of over-subscription of the shares by several times pulls our mind towards the attributes of the investing public towards the IPOs.

Table 1: IPOs by Companies during 2007-2008 and 2008-2009

Company Name	Month of Issue	IP	LP	CMP*	Percent change	SS#
Page Industries Ltd	February-07	360	449	355.6	-1.22	1.54
Advanta India Ltd	March-07	640	640	589	-7.97	4.93
Indian Bank	March-07	91	105	134.8	48.13	63.52
ICRA Ltd	March-07	330	525	411.35	24.65	75.04
Binani Cement Ltd	May-07	75	49	33	-56.00	1.58
Insecticides (India) Ltd	May-07	115	105	35.35	-69.26	1.97
Mic Electronics Ltd	May-07	150	42.05	46.85	-68.77	50.59
Dif Ltd	June-07	525	582	290.15	-44.73	3.47
ICICI Bank	June-07	890	NA	459.1	-48.42	11.5
Vishal Retail Ltd	June-07	270	472.5	87.2	-67.70	69.08

Asian Granito India Ltd	July-07	97	100.15	20.65	-78.71	4.51
Central Bank Of India	July-07	102	130.1	39.95	-60.83	62.07
Ivr Prime Urban Developers Ltd	July-07	550	500	47.9	-91.29	5.75
Omaxe Ltd	July-07	310	105	67.95	-78.08	68.34
Omnitech Info solutions Ltd	July-07	105	108	78.9	-24.86	61.84
Sel Manufacturing Co. Ltd	July-07	90	87.9	62.25	-30.83	3.62
Zylog Systems Ltd	July-07	350	525	117.6	-66.40	76.51
K P R Mill Ltd	August-07	225	201.2	91.95	-59.13	1.19
Motilal Oswal Fin. Serv. Ltd	August-07	825	999	75.1	-90.90	27.41
Take Solutions Ltd	August-07	730	876	30.7	-95.79	59.48
Consolidated Co Cons. Ltd	September-07	510	801	290	-43.14	81.18
Power Grid Corporation Ltd	September-07	52	85	75.2	44.62	64.82
Jyothy Laboratories Ltd	October-07	690	799	242.4	-64.87	47.13
Bgr Energy Systems Ltd	December-07	480	801	159.4	-66.79	145.05
Bang Overseas Ltd	January-08	207	207	236.85	14.42	2.87
Future Capital Holding	January-08	765	1044	197.95	-74.12	172.86
IRB Infrastructure	January-08	185	170	84.4	-54.38	6.1
Shriram EPC Ltd	January-08	300	290	146.85	-51.05	11.24
KNR Constructions	January-08	170	180	33.85	-80.09	1.91
Reliance Power	January-08	450	548	122.6	-72.76	122.54
Rural Electrification Corp. Ltd	February-08	105	128	70.95	-32.43	36.26
Titagarh Wagons Ltd	March-08	540	550	406.9	-24.65	7.95
Aishwarya Telecom	April-08	35	50	12.5	-64.29	21.07
Anu's Laboratories	May-08	210	260	311.25	48.21	9.05
Gokul Refoils	May-08	195	203	208.2	6.77	5.34
Niraj Cement Structures	May-08	190	185	20.25	-89.34	2.87
Birla Cotsyn(India)	June-08	14	15	4.08	-70.86	3.72
KSK Energy Ventures	June-08	240	220	144.3	-39.88	3.53
Lotus Eye Care Hosp	June-08	38	35	18.36	-51.68	3.79
Vishal Information T	July-08	150	150	340.2	126.80	1.49

Nu Tek India Ltd	August-08	192	201.1	43.55	-77.32	2.69
20 Microns Ltd	September-08	55	55	18.3	-66.73	4.29
Austral Coke And Products Ltd	September-08	196	206	78.5	-59.95	6.53

Source: http://www.chittorgarh.com/newportal/IPO_Performance_Tracker.asp

* CMP (Current Market Price) as on 4th Nov 2008

SS (Subscription Status) shows number of times over subscribed by BSE+NSE

Note: Some of the IPOs have not been considered due to lack of information

: IP- Issue Price, LP- Listing Price

IV. Performance of IPOs (2007-09):The growth of IPOs issued by Indian Companies and the amount of capital raised it can be easily interpreted that it was coming up in an increasing trend but since Feb 08 it has been decreasing. The charts below clearly depict the full story. There is a growth in the issue of IPOs by the companies since the period 2002-03. It has rose from 6 IPOs in 2002-03 to 85 IPOs in 2007-08 but decline to 21 IPOs in 2008-09. Figure1 reveals that since Jan 2008 the number of IPO issues per month has declined subsequently and gone worst since June 2008. This shows the fear and lack of confidence, among the companies, for the poor performance of the market and the global recession.

Figure 1: Number of IPOs issued during 2007 to 2009

Source: Chart prepared on the basis of data available on EPWRF Data Base Project website

Figure2 below reveals that the amount of capital raised by the Indian companies through IPOs since April 2007 has also declined. There is a 95 percent decline in the amount raised through IPOs in the period April 2008 to March 2009. This indicates the effect of the market volatility over the IPOs and hence over the capital raised by the companies.

Figure 2: Amount raised through IPOs during 2007-08 and 2008-09

Source: Chart prepared on basis of data available on EPWRF Data Base Project website

The lowering down of trade shows the closing hands of the small and medium investors towards the market. However, not only the Indian market but also World market performances were going negative day by day. According to Eichengreen and O'Rourke (2009) global stock markets fell faster during the current crisis than in 1929.

V. Findings of the Quantitative Analysis and Interpretation:

- i. The free pricing of issues permitted to certain companies had played an eminent role in the decline of the prices of the IPOs in the Indian Capital Market. The best example of this can be the issue of certain IPOs at a higher price even when there is no material earning per share and with a large public issue they bear a book value much less than its issue price. Here, it is necessary to quote the Reliance Power IPO with a price tag of Rs.450 per share for the institutional investors and Rs.430 for retail investors. The company had many projects but at rudimentary phase. Although the issue was oversubscribed due to strong track records of the promoters and the buoyant capital market but it came down to Rs.372 on its opening date itself. Just after the Reliance IPO came the IPO of EMMAAR MGF Real Estate and Wockhardt Hospital with a strong track record and prospect but were rejected by the public due to overpricing. Thus, certain issues had suffered due to the free pricing of issues granted by the SEBI.
- ii. The other important factor responsible for the downfall of the IPOs in the Indian Capital Market was the financial crisis of the US and UK economy which led to the outflow of funds by the Foreign Institutional Investors. In 2007-08, net FII inflows into India amounted to \$20.3 billion. As compared to this, the fund pulled out by them during the first nine-and-a-half months of calendar year 2008 amounted to \$11.1 billion, of which \$8.3 billion occurred over the first six-and-a-half months of financial year 2008-09 (April 1 to October 16) (Chandrasekhar, C. P. & Ghosh, J., 2008).

Figure 3: Daily movements of the SENSEX, Dec., 2007 to Sept., 2008

FII investment had an important place in driving Indian stock markets and the fact that cumulative investments by FIIs stood at \$66.5 billion at the beginning of this calendar year, the pullout triggered a collapse in stock prices. As a result, the Sensex fell from its closing peak of 20,873 on January 8, 2008, to less than 10,000 by October 17, 2008 (Figure3). In the second week of October 2008 it was noticed that the FIIs

were the net sellers in the market making their net transactions negative. This was one the worst time for all the markets in the world when all have faced sharp decline in their indices. Not only the Indian Capital Market but also the world markets such as Dow Jones, Nikkei, NASDAQ, etc showed a lowering trend in their indices.

- iii. India had noticed a high inflation rate of 10.45 percent in October 2008 and 11.49 percent in October 2009 as compared to 5.5 percent in October 2007. The inflationary conditions prevailing that time in India had increased the cost of the raw material, resulting into increase in the cost of production and lowering down the performance of the companies. This had caused the withdrawal of investors to invest.
- iv. One of the factors during the beginning of the year 2008 was the increase in the global commodity prices such as crude oil, nickel, steel, etc which led to the increase in the cost and thus lifting-up the inflation high. Although the prices of these commodities have now lowered down to almost its two-third of the price at that time but it will take time for the market to balance all the factors as at this time it is being clipped by so many factors.
- v. The growth of the IPOs and its use as a funding device by the Indian companies had been lowered down during the period 2008 to mid-2009 but there were a huge list of companies waiting for their IPO issue in the year 2010 with a proper pricing based on value to suit the investors in the currently pertaining conditions and grow with the market subsequently.

VI. Summing-up:

It is clear from above analysis that it's not the company's fundamental factors that had caused the fall in the price of the IPOs but it's the World's Financial Crisis and the free pricing of issues along with the two-digit inflation that prevailed at that time. The period from January 2008 to mid 2009 was one the worst times for all the financial markets in the world when all these markets have faced a sharp decline in their indices. The main reason for this downfall in the market indices was the financial crisis of the US and UK economy. The end of this global financial crisis became the turning point of the global market conditions. At the time when two US banks went bankrupt creating a panic in the mind of investors as a whole, the rate of sale by the FIIs had also increased. The FIIs being the purchasers were also the net sellers in the market, thus, making their net transactions negative. In fact, IPOs have always been the good source of finance to the new and existing companies and will be performing well in the coming years with improved investing route for the investors. It is simple that not only the IPOs were performing badly but also the existing reputed shares such as Reliance, Unitech Ltd, Adlabs Film Ltd, Ispat Industries, Jai Corp Ltd, etc were also among the worst performers of the year 2008 and 2009. As

per a study by the World Bank, it was expected that it would take about nine to twelve months for the market to move into better condition and the cheers on the face of the investors¹. Thus, it was high time for the investors to invest into the Group 'A' company shares because the indices were indicating a value below their potential, which regained at a faster rate when the world was out of the financial crisis. Thus, the crisis period was a real-time opportunity for long term investors who wished to skim huge benefits after the market would regain its previous trend. Those who had held fund for speculation motive with almost nine to twelve months had a good opportunity for investing into those shares which were tumbling below their potential. Although the size of the financial crisis in UK and US was unpredictable but it was quite sure to all that the world will overcome it and an inflow of funds through FIIs will improve and the market, too, will recover. Now, after half-a-decade, it is expected that the economic growth of our Nation under the leadership of Shri Narendra Modi who has aimed of making India as the most preferable place for doing business. This will not only bring a drastic change in the performance of the manufacturing sector of our country but also in the securities market.

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